

PHILOLOGICAL SCIENCES

LINGUO-PRAGMATIC ASPECT OF THE LANGUAGE OF ADVERTISING

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Abstract

This article deals with the key role of pragmatics in the linguistic analysis of advertising language. If we apply the main theory of linguistic pragmatics, that is the Theory of speech acts, to studying a speech act of advertising communication, we will find out its threefold pragmatic structure and the dominating part of implicitly articulated leading (or directing) role of the illocutionary act; the conditions of a successful advertisement analyzed. Furthermore, pragmatic functions of the implicit information are studied.

Keywords: pragmatic, advertising communication, linguistic, syntax, presupposition, semantics, knowledge, speech act.

Pragmatics was born from the philosophy of speech as a language practice. Her attitudes diverge with many provisions of linguistics, which emerged from Saussure's General Course of Linguistics. Pragmatics revises a number of principles on which previous studies were based: the priority of descriptive and representative use of language, the priority of the system and structure over its application, the priority competencies over performativity (performance of an act), the priority of language over speech. And so goes beyond the structuralist point of view, challenging the epistemological decision of Saussure to exclude from the linguistic fields of speech as a purely individual phenomenon.

The study of language signs in the 20th century was represented by two scientific approaches. The *semantic* approach interpreted the relationship of signs, words and phrases to reality or to the essence of things; these were joint studies on the subject: meaning, referent and truth (reliability). The *syntactic* approach to the study of language consisted in studying the relationship of signs to each other, words in a phrase, or phrases in a sequence of phrases. These two approaches do not exhaust either the problem of meaning or the problem of truth. There is a need for a third approach: pragmatic, analytics of language in context or the science of the contextuality of a linguistic phenomenon. Linguistic pragmatics interprets the relation of a sign to the one who creates and uses it.

Pure linguistic analysis is impossible when it goes beyond the morphosyntactic boundaries of the language as a system. The production and perception of an utterance introduces a whole complex of knowledge and intellectual operations necessary for analysis and theoretical development, for which linguistics is poorly armed. Pragmatics goes beyond closed studies applicable to a closed system of language, since it takes into account the context as an external parameter.

Linguistic pragmatics is a discipline that studies the functioning of language in speech practice, the specific manifestations of which indicate its discursive purpose. In pragmatics, language is studied as a phenomenon that is both discursive, communicative and social. Pragmatics, like semantics, deals with meaning, but with a meaning that is defined only through the use of linguistic forms. Linguistic pragmatics is designed to study the relationship of signs to users of signs, phrases - to the subjects that produce them.

Pragmatics involves syntax and semantics. It is necessary to know the relation of signs to each other and the relation of signs to things in order to consider the relation of signs to their interpreters. Syntactic rules define the relationship between carrier signs; semantic rules correlate carrier signs with other objects; the rules of pragmatics express the conditions concerning interpreters under which a carrier sign is a sign. Pragmatics determines what conditions must be met by the interpreter for the interjection "Oh", orders such as "Come here!", expressions like "Hello", and various rhetorical and poetic procedures to function. Language, in the full semiotic sense of the word, is an intersubjective set of carrier signs, the use of which is determined by syntactic, semantic and pragmatic rules [6, 34]. Pragmatically, a linguistic sign is defined by how it is used in combination with other (signs) characters, members of the same social group. To understand a language, to use it correctly, is to follow the rules of accepted usage in a given social community.

Among the numerous concepts of linguistic pragmatics for the study of advertising text, the Theory of Speech Acts seems especially relevant, since it determines the expediency of utterance, the ultimate goal pursued by the speaker in the process of generating utterance. Robert Stalnaker, engaged in formal semantics, establishes in 1972 a clear difference between the two disciplines, semantics and pragmatics. So, syntax studies phrases, semantics - propositions, pragmatics

studies linguistic acts and contexts, in which they are committed.

Pragmatics has two tasks:

- analyze illocutionary acts;
- characterize the features of the context of the statement, which help to determine the proposition expressed by this phrase [6, 44].

The problem of the analysis of speech acts is to find the necessary and sufficient conditions for a successful result, or, simply, for the normal performance of a speech act. These conditions include the presence or absence some characteristic features in the context, in which the speech act is performed. For example: the speaker's intention, knowledge, views, beliefs. And also the expectations and interests common to the speaker and the perceiver, the place and time of the utterance, its effect, the reliability of the expressed proposition, etc. All of these aspects are fully relevant and meet the goals and objectives of the advertising text.

The theory of speech acts as a fundamental theoretical concept of linguistic pragmatics was expounded by the English logician J. Austin in a course of lectures published in 1962, and in Russian under the name "Word as action" [1, 22-129]. Subsequently, these ideas were developed by his follower, the American logician J. Searle. In the theory of speech acts, a linguistic statement is considered as an action that the speaker performs in order to achieve a specific goal. The essence of this doctrine comes down to the fact that linguistic statements exist not only for to report on the state of affairs in the world and qualify as true or false, but also in order to carry out certain actions with their help.

Any statement can be descriptive with the inclusion of performativity (a performative statement is equivalent to an action). For example, a statement like: *It's cold in this room* can be true and be ascertaining, but it can have an illocutionary meaning that turns the statement into an indirect speech act (a request to open a window, an invitation to leave the room, etc.).

Former logical-philosophical interpretations of the use of language considered the statement from the standpoint of its truth or falsity relative to reality. But this limitation of language use does not give a complete picture of the world, does not reflect the relation of the utterance to the speaker and the addressee. According to the theory of speech acts, any communicative act has a tripartite structure. Any speech act can be considered as: a locutionary act - from the standpoint of the use of linguistic means; illocutionary act - regarding the goal of the speaker in a certain context; perlocutionary act - from the point of view of the impact on the addressee. So John Austin introduced new concepts: locutionary, illocutionary and perlocutionary acts. The locutionary act is an act of reference (said as such). An illocutionary act, which is the action for which a phrase is spoken. Perlocutionary act - an act that is realized by the fact of speaking. For Austin, all three structural levels of the same speech act do not have the same status in linguistic terms. Here is one of the examples proposed by the scientist to illustrate this difference:

Locutionary act: *He told me: "You can't do it."* Illocutionary act: *He protested against my action.* Perlocutionary act: *He dissuaded me, kept me, he stopped*

me, brought me to reason, and so on. He bored me. [7, 212].

Between the locutionary and illocutionary aspects, apparently, there are connections of a conditional order, and only analysis allows them to differentiate. On the contrary, no conditional connection can determine the relationship between the illocutionary aspect and the perlocutionary. The illocutionary aspect is a given amount of code as being relatively predictable. The perlocutionary aspect is nothing more than an unpredictable consequence, devoid of any necessity. Therefore, Austin excludes from his theory study of the perlocutionary aspect.

A student and follower of John Austin, the American philosopher John Rogers Searle continues to study the theory of speech acts proposed by John Austin and in the article Classification of speech acts proposes a new taxonomy of illocutionary acts, which has become generally accepted [4, 170-194].

Five categories of illocutionary acts are considered:

1. Assertives - i.e. acts, the essence of which is that the speaker, by means of a speech act, assumes the obligation to vouch for the truth of the proposition expressed in the act.

[Verbs: *affirm, deny, answer, object*, etc.].

2. Directives - i.e. acts, the essence of which is that the speaker, through a speech act, tries to induce the listener to do something.

[Verbs: *ask, order, command, beg, allow, invite, advise*, etc.].

3. Commissions - i.e. acts, the essence of which is that the speaker, by means of a speech act, assumes the obligation to do something in the future.

[Verbs: *promise, pledge, take a vow, take an oath, give a word, vouch, take on obligations*, etc.].

4. Expressives - i.e. acts, the essence of which is that the speaker expresses his psychological state through a speech act.

[Verbs: *thank, congratulate, apologize, condole, express approval, express disapproval*, etc.].

5. Declarations - i.e. acts, the essence of which is that the speaker, through a speech act, makes a statement, proclaims.

[Verbs: *give a name, baptize, declare war, issue a decree (law, decree), resign*, etc.]

In other words, the illocutionary act performed by uttering a sentence is a function of the linguistic meaning of the given sentence. [4, 151].

Illocutionary acts implemented in advertising messages belong to categories I and II of illocutionary acts, i.e. to assertives - approving acts which are responsible for the truth of the expressed proposition and directives - guiding acts aimed at inducing the recipient of the message to purchase the advertised object.

Applying the Speech Act Theory to the analysis of an advertising communicative act, three parameters of an advertising communication speech act can be distinguished [5, 24]. The first two come down to linguistic communication. The first parameter is locutionary (creation of a written text and image), which characterizes the speech act in relation to the language means used. The second parameter is illocutionary, it characterizes

the speech act in its relation to the goal and conditions. This parameter is related to the result of the illocutionary act, to the reaction of the reader inclined or not to buy the advertised product.

Advertising communication has semiotic and pragmatic components:

- In *locutionary* plan, an act is represented simultaneously by text and image.

- In *illocutionary* plan, we can talk about two mutually complementary components: a descriptive, informing component, expressed by a stating act, and an argumentative component, prompting the addressee to make a purchase. In this regard, advertising communication is informational and convincing. At this stage of the analysis, the indirect nature of advertising communication is generally taken into account, where the illocutionary guiding act dominates. [*I advise you to buy this product*], expressed mostly implicitly. The guiding act is hidden behind the ascertaining act. Advertising makes a series of statements about the product and the consumer, for example, that the product is new, of such and such a quality, that the consumer using it is satisfied, but for those who do not use this product, it is just that it is not enough. *An illocutionary act that dominates most advertisements, explicitly stating and implicitly directing.*

- In *perlocutionary* plan, the desire or intention to buy a product is the perlocutionary effect produced by the announcement. Advertising discourse is a complex indirect speech act. The pragmatic meaning of his statement is different from literal (semantic) content, where the speaker's illocutionary goal is directly manifested with the help of vocabulary. In advertising messages, information is encoded using linguistic means and is presented implicitly. Implicit information assigns an increased evaluative value to the object and, unlike ready-made information, is perceived without criticism and doubt, is little controlled by consciousness and is used for manipulation. The effectiveness of implicit information is based on a complex mechanism for its extraction and interpretation by the addressee [2, 209]. The pragmatic function of implicit information in advertising is its impact on the addressee. For advertising strategy, the most important type of implicit information is presupposition.

The pragmatic presupposition is a central element in characterizing the advertising context. In any statement, it is possible to single out the statement contained

in it (explicit information) and presuppositions (implicit information) - those background aspects of the content of the statement that are not subject to doubt. Presuppositions form a condition for the meaningfulness of the statement, as they relate to the knowledge and beliefs of the sender and addressee.

To avoid misunderstanding, it is preferable that participants in the same context share the same presuppositions. Presuppositions shared by interlocutors in a situation of linguistic communication are important elements of the advertising context. If the addressee does not know anything about any judgment, the presupposition is untenable. This inconsistency does not lead to a communicative failure, moreover, undivided presuppositions are often used in advertising communication models, where information is differentiated and presented in stages, provoking interest in the subject of advertising.

Thus, in the pragmatic structure of advertising communication, the illocutionary act is represented by two components: an affirmative act through explicit descriptive and informing content and a guiding act through an argumentative and persuasive impact. Moreover, the illocutionary guiding act dominates and is veiled by the affirmative-evaluative act. An advertising message is a complex indirect speech act, where implicit information has a pronounced pragmatic function - an impact on the addressee.

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